

An Experimental Approach to the Perception of Empathy in Speech

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Abstract. With advances in the techniques and naturalness of speech synthesis, and the increasing commercial contexts in which it is used, the need for natural affective synthesis has grown. There is a need to understand the acoustic correlates of emotions in natural speech to optimise this affective synthesis, particularly regarding ‘secondary emotions’ like empathy. This original research seeks to shed more light on the nature of empathy in speech, using a parametric approach to synthesis. Although an older technique compared to machine learning synthesis, it is found that this approach allows for a greater degree of control over acoustic correlates, and allows for a more precise image of empathy to emerge. This research splits empathy into production and perception; the first experiment looks at the difference between non-empathetic and empathetic contexts in a dialogue context with 10 participants (5 male and 5 female, in pairs), which allows for the identification of empathetic correlates in natural speech production. Following this, an experiment using resynthesised versions of the non-empathetic productions explores which combinations and amounts of the correlates observed in the first experiment (including pitch, duration, and voice quality) must be used in order to elicit empathy. In doing so, it becomes clear that empathy is not a unified concept in speech, instead behaving differently within and between production and perception.

Keywords: phonetics; empathy; resynthesis; affective synthesis

1 Introduction

1.1 Empathy

Language does not exist in a vacuum in relation to other human and sociological phenomena. Any investigation into the manifestation of emotions in speech needs to begin with an understanding of how emotions relate to one another. Becker and Wachsmuth (2006) note that in order to model emotions into a socially-intelligent agent capable of communicating with and relating to others (in which speech clearly plays a part), one must first explore theories of emotion. One common starting point is to divide emotion into two types: primary and secondary. Primary emotions are typically defined as emotions that are innate, supporting reactive response behaviour and tending not to involve higher-level processing (Becker & Wachsmuth, 2006; James et al., 2018), whereas secondary emotions rely on this higher-level processing. Primary emotions can be ‘understood as a prototypical emotion types [sic] which can already be ascribed to one year old children’ (Becker-Asano & Wachsmuth, 2008, p. 3). As noted by Kemper (1987), there are large variations in what are considered to be primary, arguing for four (fear, anger, depression, satisfaction), where others argue for as few as two (Brenner, 1980) or as many as eleven (Emde, 1980). There appears to be a cross-cultural universality of primary emotions: Ekman (1973) found that fear, anger, sadness, happiness, disgust, and surprise were similarly realised across a number of unrelated languages and cultures.

This implies that the manner of primary emotions' realisation in speech is consistent or mostly-consistent across languages.

Due to being more sociologically-conditioned, secondary emotions such as empathy are more subjective. Conclusions about their realisation in speech are limited to the cultures and contexts in which they are observed. Secondary emotions require a higher level of cognitive processing (James et al., 2018), and build on the ability to evaluate preferences over outcomes and expectations (Becker-Asano & Wachsmuth, 2008).

Empathy is a secondary emotion, combining the influences of self/other state and inherent traits (Cuff et al., 2016). There is a divide, particularly in research on personality and developmental disorders, between cognitive and affective empathy, where affective empathy is not consciously elicited, but cognitive empathy can consciously manipulate these affective elements (Cuff et al., 2016). There is no clear means of dividing these two types of empathy when studying its manifestation in speech, but it can be assumed that in acted speech contexts, cognitive elements are being employed. However, because this distinction cannot be explicitly made, the term 'empathy' will be used in this study without subdivision, and further work will be needed to understand how these two types differ in speech. For the purposes of this study, empathy is defined as when the emotion felt by one person is felt by another person, allowing them to emotionally respond in a manner appropriate to the situation. As a result of its status as a secondary emotion, empathy may occur in different degrees (Boukricha et al., 2013), and may vary across languages.

Sympathy and compassion are two distinct concepts that are commonly confused with empathy (Cuff et al., 2016), but they are not the same as empathy. Singer and Lamm (2009) give the example of empathising with a person who is feeling sad, which produces a feeling of being sad in the self. Sympathy, on the other hand, will cause a feeling of pity for the other, and compassion will create a feeling of compassionate love for the other, but neither will cause the same feeling of sadness. Empathy is also not just mimicry or emotional contagion: while they are low-level contributors to empathy, they do not account for the whole experience of empathy (Singer & Lamm, 2009). Additionally, these processes seem to be largely automatic (Hatfield et al., 2014), which rules them out from being secondary in the sense that empathy is.

1.2 Empathy in Natural Speech

In studying the realisation of empathy in speech, the same correlates are explored as are used for studying other emotions like anger or joy. These studies of other emotions employ pitch, duration, and intensity in particular (Erickson, 2005), although voice quality (Gobl et al., 2002) and articulatory precision are also frequently included (Cahn, 1990; Murray & Arnott, 1995; Schröder, 2001). These same correlates are explored for empathy; the correlates at our disposal are typically considered to be pitch, duration, loudness, and voice quality (Laver, 1994). There is reason to assume that these are all manipulated in the production of empathy, and no reason to assume the existence of other major influencing correlates.

Pitch can be manipulated by a speaker to realise emotions through raising or lowering the entire pitch level, or they can reduce the pitch span by widening or flattening the pitch contour. Busso et al., (2009) found both of these features to be important in emotional communication, although with more focus on pitch level than contour. Their paper leaves open the question of whether there are particular parts of an utterance that are more affected by these changes and thus more salient for empathy.

As with pitch, there are two different types of duration changes that can be observed, these being global and temporal (or local) speech rate (Mozziconacci & Hermes, 2000). Global speech rate, commonly

referred to as just ‘speech rate’ in the literature (Burkhardt & Sendlmeier, 2000; McHenry et al., 2012), refers to the number of segments produced over time in a whole utterance. Local speech rate is a measure of segment length. Mozziconacci and Hermes (2000) explored a number of primary emotions, asking participants to rank durational deviations from neutral by how well they expressed a given emotion. They found that speakers ranked changes in global duration anywhere from a 9% deviation (for fear), all the way to a 31% deviation (for boredom) as optimal for different emotions. Deviations perceived as optimal ranged from +25% to -31% and differed in most cases from changes found in their production study. These results correspond with those found in other studies (Bezooijen, 2011), including in unrelated languages like Japanese (Kitahara & Tokhura, 1992). McHenry et al. (2012) looked at three secondary emotions: ‘caring’, ‘sympathetic’ and ‘competent,’ as classified by an oncologist, a psychiatrist, and a clinical psychologist. They found smaller deviations from neutral speech rate than Mozziconacci and Hermes (2000). Speakers increased speech rate between 5% (‘competent’) and 8.6% (‘sympathetic’). Therefore, if there is a change in duration for empathetic speech, it is likely to lie in the region of these secondary emotions, but there is scope for duration change to deviate further from neutral.

Studies of the perception of empathy in speech have investigated the same correlates as for other emotions. Xiao et al. (2015), for example, focus on speech rate as a cue for empathy in therapist communication in American English. McHenry et al. (2012) also focus on speech rate, finding it to be reduced in empathetic contexts alongside reduced pitch in their statistical study of empathetic communication (American English). Weiste and Peräkylä (2014) conducted a qualitative rather than statistical analysis of empathetic communication in a therapy context (Finnish), and found that mimicry of a patient’s intonation and voice quality was a signal of empathy. Clearly, therefore, there are variations in the ways in which empathy is claimed to be realised in speech, but whether this is a case of language, cultural or situational context, or experimental method is unclear. Nevertheless, despite differences in results, it is clear that the correlates focused on are some (but not all) of those used in the study of other emotions in speech.

Empathy in speech is vital to understand due to its social and developmental role as a marker of self/other discrimination (Asada, 2015). This split allows for socially-intelligent agents (either human or robot) to assume a social role in relation to others, as well as allowing for perspective-taking, which has clear purpose in inter-personal relations. In understanding empathy in speech, we understand the manifestation of these crucial human-human interactions, and it is then possible to model these into human-robot interactions as well (Asada, 2015).

1.3 Parametric Synthesis

Speech synthesis, and the resynthesis of natural speech, are useful tools in the investigation of the correlates of empathy. Machine learning approaches to speech synthesis (and expressive synthesis in particular) can replicate natural speech with great ease and accuracy, although using a parametric synthesis technique is more effective for exploring the manipulation of correlates to understand emotions in speech.

The effectiveness of machine learning approaches is not to be ignored, however: Tacotron (Wang et al., 2017), an end-to-end synthesis approach that produces spectrograms from text inputs, was found to outperform production parametric systems, and could be trained to produce expressive output (based on richly expressive but noisy data) from scratch with a random initialisation (Wang et al., 2017). However, since the system is fully end-to-end, there is little that can be gleaned in terms of which features the system is identifying as salient in emotional speech, and how they are reproduced by the system. The only thing

that can be learned from this system is that it is possible to produce expressive speech outputs using a neural network, and nothing about the correlates of the emotions themselves.

Similarly using a voice-AI system, but adding features that focus on acoustic correlates, Cohn and Zellou (2019) demonstrated that with the Amazon Alexa ‘speechcons’ (Amazon, 2021), pitch and duration could be altered to make certain words sound more ‘expressive’. Altering pitch and duration is a step towards understanding how these correlates factor into expressive speech, and it was demonstrated that these expressive speechcons aid human vocal alignment towards the voice-AI (Cohn & Zellou, 2019). However, there is no explanation of what ‘more expressive’ actually means in terms of emotional output, and additionally there is no room for understanding the gradience of emotions, since there are only the ‘regular’ and ‘expressive’ possibilities.

It is clear therefore that machine learning methods can provide the most effective techniques for replicating the human voice, which allows for more trustworthy and engaging social agents (Yalçın, 2019). This is a key step in achieving the manifestation of self/other distinctions and relations as realised in empathy. However, the amount that we can learn about the processes of emotional perception and production through synthesis is limited. Clearly, the end-to-end systems do not provide a means to investigate which correlates have been identified as salient. Even non-end-to-end synthesis systems that use statistical parametric synthesis cannot tell us much about which correlates are necessary for elicitation of emotions such as empathy. EMPHASIS (Li et al., 2018), which uses a cascade model, groups features that are relevant to different emotions in the input layer. However, the features that this system uses automatically to generate emotions such as empathy cannot be made explicit, and the correlates used to encode and decode emotional speech remain hidden. As such, using older techniques such as formant synthesis are more useful for advancing the theoretical understanding of how emotions like empathy are produced in speech.

Older models, based on formant synthesis and parametric approaches, may produce less natural speech, but grant a much greater degree of control over individual correlates, which will aid in understanding emotional speech. This is often achieved using formant synthesisers, which derive approximations to a speech waveform (Klatt, 1980). For example, Klatt's original (1980) synthesiser, based on the Liljencrants-Fant Model (Fant et al., 1985), offered 39 control parameters, which allows for specific alterations in acoustic features. This allows for greater understanding of encoding emotions in speech. Additionally, many formant synthesisers are commercially-available and easy to use (Bangayan et al., 1997), so although the output is far less realistic than the most up-to-date methods, they are far more practical for understanding emotional speech.

Parametric alteration of acoustic correlates for affective synthesis, as with the study of productions of natural affective speech, tends to focus on pitch, duration, voice quality, and precision of articulation in various combinations. Cahn's (1990) Affect Editor manipulates pitch, duration, and articulatory precision to produce various primary emotions. Murray and Arnott (1995) build on Cahn's model by adding Voice Quality, as do Schröder (2001) and Burkhardt and Sendmeier (2000). These parametric syntheses can still be incorporated into models of emotions in socially-intelligent agents. Kismet (Breazeal, 2001) uses the AVS model (Arousal-Valence Space) to plot the relationships between different emotions in the system. One of the most common mappings of emotions is the PAD-space (Pleasure-Arousal-Dominance) (Park et al., 2011), which opts for a three-dimensional mapping of the emotional space for an agent. In order to realise this emotional framework in speech, some means of affective synthesis is required, and parametric synthesis techniques are perfectly sufficient to fulfil this role, although with the caveat above that naturalness may be slightly lessened compared to machine-learning techniques.

It is therefore a parametric approach that shall be used in this research, since the greater degree of control over correlates and greater transparency in producing affective synthesis renders it far superior for understanding and recreating the true correlates of emotions in speech. Although the methods are not the most up-to-date, a parametric approach to synthesis provides the best toolkit for the task at hand, as well as being more commercially-available and accessible than cutting-edge machine learning techniques. Additionally, the findings from this research can still be incorporated into artificial emotional frameworks like the AVS model or PAD-space.

1.4 Aims of this Study

This study explores the perception and production of empathy in speech in a British English and non-clinical context. Previous studies (such as McHenry et al., 2012; and Weiste & Peräkylä, 2014) focus on languages and dialects other than British English, and focus on empathy in clinical contexts such as therapy (Weiste & Peräkylä, 2014) or oncology (McHenry et al., 2012). The correlates that are being focused on will be the same as those studied in other empathetic (and general emotional) speech studies, these being pitch, duration, and voice quality. Due to the experimental methodology not guaranteeing fixed distance from the microphone during recording, as well as Praat's resynthesis tools normalising intensity, the correlate of intensity will not be explored, although evidence does suggest some salience in other kinds of emotional speech (Erickson, 2005), as well as in empathy (Alam et al., 2018). The case is the same for articulatory precision: although it is perceptually salient in some emotional productions (Murray & Arnott, 1995), it could not be feasibly produced or assessed in the present work.

The first study (Section 2) explores empathy in speech production, using acted speech dialogues between pairs of participants to determine which correlates explored are salient to empathy, as well as if other factors such as gender are relevant to the production of empathetic speech. The second study (Section 3) manipulates these same correlates for a perception test, where samples from the first experiment are resynthesised. The gradient of empathetic speech is unknown (Boukricha et al., 2013), and this is also explored in this study. The results are considered jointly in Section 4, and Section 5 concludes and suggests further directions for this work.

2 Production Study

2.1 Methodology

2.1.1 Design

Ten participants were selected for this experiment (five male and five female), all speakers of British English and aged between 20 and 26. Participation was voluntary and participants were not compensated. To elicit productions of empathy, the participants were paired and asked to read eight different dialogues, each preceded by a short scenario description (e.g., 'A and B are discussing difficulties in a relationship'). Each dialogue had a stimulus phrase that was placed into both a non-empathetic and empathetic context, and was one of the following: 'I know where you're coming from,' 'That's hard,' 'I understand,' and 'I hear what you're saying' (labelled from 1 to 4 accordingly). For example, 'I know where you're coming from' was placed into a dialogue where A asks B for directions, and also in a dialogue where A and B are

discussing work stress over a coffee (the full list of dialogues can be found in Appendix One). Half of the participants produced Stimuli 1 and 2, and the other half produced 3 and 4.

Participants were paired as follows:

Table 1: Participant Pairings.

Participant One (Stimuli 1 and 2)	Participant Two (Stimuli 3 and 4)
1F	1M
2F	2M
4M	3M
3F	4F
5M	5F

Participants were recorded in a recording booth using a Sennheiser ME-64 microphone, recorded onto a MixPre-6 recorder (256kbps, 48kHz) at a distance of around 50 centimetres (resulting from the room size and participants sharing a microphone). They were instructed to read through the dialogues twice, clapping once at the end of each dialogue, and twice at the end of the full set, as this created spikes in the waveform that made it easier to distinguish the recordings during analysis. One pair, 3F and 4F, had to re-record the full set, as they accidentally switched parts halfway through. For all recordings, the second set of dialogues was used for analysis unless there was disruption to the recording, on the basis that speakers were more comfortable with the dialogues after having read them through once already.

The recordings were trimmed using Audacity so that only the stimuli remained, and Praat was used for analysis. Different analyses were conducted for different correlates being explored. For pitch, there were two different strategies that could have been used by speakers. The first is changing the pitch contour, which is a well-attested correlate of emotional speech (Busso et al., 2009), as well as a raising or lowering of the overall pitch, which is noted as a correlate of empathy in bad news discussion by McHenry et al. (2012). To measure the variations both in overall pitch and contour, or 'level' and 'span' (Ladd, 2008), I employed a method modelled on Graham (2014), which, instead of comparing the entire pitch contour, uses Patterson's (2000) method to plot pitch onto tonal targets. This was chosen on the assumption that speakers are manipulating tonal targets to alter prosody, rather than abstractly changing the pitch contour, and so these targets are key in understanding how pitch was modified for empathy. Using the ToBI system and using Praat (with pitch set to the autocorrelation method), the pitch was recorded at the onset, H and L* for shorter stimuli (2 and 3), and for the longer stimuli (1 and 4), at the Onset, initial H* (iH*), L, H* and final low (FL). Span, as a means of measuring the width of the pitch contour, was determined by subtracting FL from iH* for longer stimuli and L* from H for shorter ones. The full list of pitch measurements is found in Appendix Two.

For duration, there were also two types of change measures, these being global and temporal (or local) duration, both different kinds of speech rate (Mozziconacci & Hermes, 2000). Global duration was measured by comparing the lengths of the stimuli between the non-empathetic and empathetic conditions, under the logic that the number of segments produced in the utterance would be the same for both conditions, and so measuring total length was sufficient for a measure of rate. Local speech rate was ascertained by measuring the length of the first accented vowel (iH* for Stimuli 1 and 4 and L* for Stimuli 2 and 3).

The only voice quality that appeared aside from modal voice was creaky voice, which typically arises from a low frequency vocal fold vibration and low F_0 (Laver, 1980), caused by slack, thick, and compressed vocal folds with a short vibrating length (Keating et al., 2015). The level of creak was measured by subtracting the amplitude of the second harmonic (H2) from that of the first (H1), which is a common way to measure creaky voice (Keating et al., 2015). This was done using a Praat Script to extract the spectrum of the vowel being analysed, and manually finding H1 and H2 values.

2.1.2 COVID-19 Adjustments

The recordings in this experiment took place during the second national COVID-19 lockdown, and consequently measures were taken to ensure the utmost safety of participants. This included sanitisation of the recording area, social distancing and wearing masks where possible, and ensuring recordings were taken as soon after a negative asymptomatic swab test as possible. One male participant had to be replaced as a result of a positive swab test, and three female participants had to be replaced as a result of rapidly-changing travel plans in response to the pandemic.

Additionally, the building containing the recording facilities was locked for the duration of the Christmas vacation, which meant that the recording of 3M and 4M had to take place in an empty room, using a mobile phone with recording quality set to the maximum of 256kbps and 48kHz, since 4M had to be found last-minute as a replacement for the other male participant who contracted COVID-19, delaying the recording. There was echo interference in this recording, which made it impossible to measure voice quality, but analysis of duration in was still possible once the dynamic range was changed from 90dB to 70dB.

2.2 Results

2.2.1 Pitch

Figure 1: *Difference in Mean Pitch by Condition.*

Figure 2: *Difference in Mean Pitch by Stimulus.*

There is a clean divide between stimulus length in relation to pitch level as a cue for empathy. For long utterances, a repeated measures ANOVA was conducted with five levels (onset, iH*, L, H*, FL), with condition (non-empathetic and empathetic), stimulus (4 or 1, these being the two longer utterances) and gender as between-subject factors. This ANOVA revealed strong significance between pitch level and condition ($F(4, 40)=8.932$, $p<0.001$), being lower in the empathetic condition (as illustrated in Figure 1), as well as pitch level and stimulus produced ($F(4,40)=4.701$, $p=0.003$), where Stimulus 1 had a lower pitch level than Stimulus 4 (Figure 2). Three-way effects of pitch level, condition, and gender ($F(4,40)=2.414$, $p=0.065$) and pitch level, condition, and stimulus ($F(4,40)=2.434$, $p=0.063$) were found to be approaching significance, which is promising given the sample size. Gender was revealed to be insignificant in relation to pitch level ($F(4,40)=1.432$, $p=0.241$).

Individual ANOVAs were conducted for each pitch point, to see which pitch points were most salient for this difference in pitch level. It was found that only iH* was significant between conditions, but this was a strong significance ($F(1,16)=10.333$, $p=0.005$). This can be seen in Figure 1, as the difference in mean pitch level for non-empathetic and empathetic conditions is much greater for iH* than other points.

For shorter utterances, a repeated measures ANOVA was also conducted, with three levels (onset, H, and L*), and between subject factors as stimulus (2 or 3 this time), condition, and gender (both as before). Unlike for the longer utterances, this ANOVA revealed no significance between pitch level and any other factors. Individual ANOVAs for each pitch point also revealed no significant effects, which suggests that pitch level manipulations for empathy are limited to longer utterances.

Figure 3: Differences in Mean Pitch Span by Condition and Stimulus.

Span was determined by subtracting the FL pitch from the iH* pitch for longer utterances, and L* pitch from the H pitch for shorter utterances. The results for difference in mean span between condition and stimulus are found in Figure 3. An ANOVA revealed that condition was strongly significant for longer utterances ($F(1,12)=12.102$, $p=0.001$) and showed a large decrease between non-empathetic and empathetic, but not significant at all for shorter ones ($F(1,12)=0.275$, $p=0.61$). Stimulus was also found to be significant for longer utterances ($F(1,12)=6.615$, $p=0.024$), where stimulus 4 showed a much larger span difference, and no other effects were found in the data. This suggests that span decrease between conditions and stimuli is again more salient for longer utterances.

2.2.2 Duration

Using a paired samples t test, it was found that global duration difference for Stimulus 1 was approaching significance ($t(4)=-2.44$, $p=0.071$), which is promising given the sample size, although still insignificant. No significance was found for Stimulus 2 ($t(4)=0.656$, $p=0.548$), Stimulus 3 ($t(4)=-0.453$, $p=0.674$), or Stimulus 4 ($t(4)=1.335$, $p=0.253$). The difference between the two conditions (non-empathetic minus empathetic), as well as the % change from the non-empathetic condition, can be found in Appendix Two. Figure 4 demonstrates the difference between condition for global duration by stimulus.

Figure 4: *Global Duration Difference by Condition and Stimulus.*

Local duration was found to be significant particularly in shorter stimuli according to Huggins' (1972) Just-Noticeable Difference (JND) for segment length in natural speech, where an increase of 1ms or decrease of 2ms was deemed to be significant. It was significant only in 50% of longer stimuli, whereas for shorter stimuli it was significant in 80% (Table 2; values over this JND are italicised). To ensure that this was not an effect of pre-boundary lengthening, since temporal expansion at prosodic phrase edges is common, (Fletcher, 2010), the final segment lengths of the longer stimuli were measured. The segment lengthening was only significant for 20% of cases, and only within Stimulus 1 (Table 3), and so the duration effect seen in shorter stimuli is an empathy cue rather than pre-boundary lengthening.

Table 2: *Duration Change in First Accented Syllable.*

Stimulus 1		Stimulus 2		Stimulus 3		Stimulus 4	
Partici pant	Change (ms)	Partici pant	Change (ms)	Partici pant	Change (ms)	Partici pant	Change (ms)
1F	+0.2	1F	-7.7	1M	+2.4	1M	-1.5
2F	+0.5	2F	+11.4	2M	-3.4	2M	+0.7
3F	-8.6	3F	-1.1	4F	-9.3	4F	-2.1
4M	+4	4M	-6.1	3M	+10.3	3M	-6.5
5M	-1.4	5M	+2.4	5F	-0.2	5F	+4.7

Table 3: *Final Segment Lengthening.*

Stimulus 1		Stimulus 2		Stimulus 3		Stimulus 4	
Partici pant	Change (ms)	Partici pant	Change (ms)	Partici pant	Change (ms)	Partici pant	Change (ms)
1F	0	1F	-7.7	1M	+2.4	1M	+0.2
2F	+4.9	2F	+11.4	2M	-3.4	2M	+0.3
3F	+0.5	3F	-1.1	4F	-9.3	4F	+0.2
4M	+6.3	4M	-6.1	3M	+10.3	3M	0
5M	-0.4	5M	+2.4	5F	-0.2	5F	+0.9

2.2.3 Voice Quality

The measurements of H1-H2 for each speaker's long and short stimuli are listed in Appendix Two (3M and 4M are omitted due to recording quality). An ANOVA was conducted, with H1-H2 as the dependent variable, and speaker gender, condition (non-empathetic or empathetic), and stimulus length (short or long) as the factors. This test revealed no significant effects for condition or stimulus length, but showed a strong significance for gender ($F(1, 24)=12.5, p=0.002$). Gender was not found to be significant when combined with other factors such as condition ($F(1,24)=0.183, p=0.673$) or length ($F(1, 24)=0.280, p=0.601$). Male speakers used creaky voice (indicated by a negative or small positive H1-H2 value) to a far greater degree than female speakers (as illustrated in Figure 5), so while creaky voice is a reliable cue for speaker gender, it is not a reliable cue for empathetic speech.

Figure 5: Mean H1-H2 for Male and Female Speakers.

2.3 Discussion

The results of the production study demonstrate that there are correlates responsible for the elicitation of empathy in speech, but their behaviour is not identical across all empathetic productions. The main factor deciding which correlates employed is the length of the production. Empathy in longer utterances was elicited by a significant decrease in pitch level, centred around the first accent (iH*), as well as significant reduction in pitch span. For shorter utterances, on the other hand, it was found that empathy was elicited by a significant increase in local duration. Global duration change and voice quality were not found to be markers of empathy.

A number of general points must be considered before the data presented above is analysed. Firstly, as a result of the methodology demanding acted speech, the phrases chosen for this experiment were fixed, which means that they may not have been natural for the participants and could have changed the realisation of empathy. After participating, 5M commented that he felt the phrases in the dialogues were not ones he would have chosen to be empathetic. The extent to which meaning factors into productions of empathy is unclear, and requires further work.

In terms of pitch, the difference between the results for longer and shorter stimuli indicate that pitch is a far better marker of empathy in longer utterances than shorter ones. The lowering of pitch in the empathetic condition supports McHenry et al.'s (2012) study in American English, which demonstrates the same decrease in pitch in empathetic scenarios. The significance of only the iH* in longer utterances as an individual pitch point suggests that this is also an extremely localised effect in terms of what is being manipulated, focused on the first accent in an utterance. For pitch level, it may be that no significance is realised in shorter utterances because the first (and only) accent is attached to an L rather than an H, but work on short utterances where the first accent is attached to an H would be needed to confirm this. The reduction in pitch level is also accompanied by a reduction in pitch span in longer utterances, something

again not seen in shorter utterances, which suggests that the two are connected in pitch-based productions of empathy.

The shorter stimuli showing no significance in pitch level or span between conditions complicates the image of McHenry et al.'s (2012) unified portrayal of empathetic speech, especially in light of the fact that local-level duration is far more salient for shorter utterances than longer utterances. This suggests a sensitivity to length that goes against the idea of empathy having a single realisation.

The significant stimulus difference for longer utterances, where stimulus 4 showed a larger span and higher level, can be explained by looking at the context of Dialogue 6 ('Speaker A is trying to do a video call with Speaker B'). Stimulus 4 (non-empathetic) was contained in this dialogue, and the context seemed to trigger the Lombard effect, where speakers commonly increase vocal intensity and fundamental frequency in noisy environments or when there are difficulties being heard (Garnier & Henrich, 2014). Therefore, had this not occurred, it is possible that the inter-stimulus difference would not be significant, as demonstrated by the fact that there was no inter-stimulus difference for shorter utterances, where the pragmatic content was different but there was no elicitation of the Lombard Effect.

The increased reliance on durational cues in shorter utterances, as shown by the results for local duration change, show that correlates of empathy change with utterance length. It is not simply the case that shorter utterances show no significant changes in empathetic contexts, as would be concluded with pitch alone. The insignificance for all stimuli of global duration, despite the mean percentage deviation for each stimulus being roughly that of changes found in previous studies, suggests that the effect observed is more specific than just speech rate. Even though speech rate tends to affect stressed syllables more than unstressed syllables (and vowels more than consonants) (Burkhardt & Sendlmeier, 2000), a change in speech rate would still affect the duration of the entire utterance, which does not happen to significance in any circumstance here.

Gender did not significantly contribute to any results apart from the use of creaky voice, where there was no significant difference between the non-empathetic and empathetic conditions, or gender and condition combined. Creaky voice is therefore a better signal of the gender of the speaker than a cue for empathy. This creak was much stronger for male speakers than it was for female speakers, which agrees with cross-dialectal studies that find that male speech usually contains more creak (c.f. Podesva, 2011).

2.3.1 Interim Conclusions and Implications for Resynthesis

These results do not fully correspond with previous studies on the production of empathy in speech. This difference between prediction and empirical results could come from a number of sources, such as the fact that the speech was acted rather than natural as it was in previous studies, or the use of British English as the speaker dialect, or the more everyday speech context, instead of being a clinical context. Nevertheless, the elicitation of empathy in these results seems to be much more guided by the length of the utterance, where longer utterances rely more on manipulation of pitch level and pitch span, and shorter ones more on local-level duration change. Creaky voice played no part in the signalling of empathy, instead serving to be a marker of gender rather than emotional state. Therefore, it is expected that pitch level, pitch span, and local-level duration will be the most salient correlates of empathy in the perception study.

3 Assessing Perceptions of Empathy through Analysis-by-Synthesis

In the production study, strong relationships were found between pitch level and span and empathy for longer utterances, and local duration and empathy for shorter ones. The perception study aims to see if these correlates can be reproduced through resynthesis, and if they still communicate empathy to the same significance as in the production study. This tests to see if listeners prefer a certain correlate or set of correlates in perceiving empathy, and if this corresponds to the correlates produced by the speakers. It additionally tests to see if empathetic speech is perceived as gradient.

3.1 Methodology

3.1.1 *Production of Resynthesised Samples*

One male and female production of a longer stimulus and a shorter stimulus, both non-empathetic, were chosen to be resynthesised using the correlates found in the production study. Stimulus 1 was chosen to avoid interference from the Lombard Effect, and speakers 5M and 2F were the samples chosen. The shorter utterance chosen was Stimulus 3, and 1M and 4F were chosen as samples.

It was decided that intonational manipulations (pitch level and widened/flattened contour) would be grouped (per Burkhardt & Sendlmeier (2000)) and applied to longer utterances, and local duration effects would be manipulated in shorter samples. This was to maximise the potential for significant results according to the production study, and also because combining all correlates in different quantities would have resulted in thousands of samples, which was not possible with the resources available. There was a chance that speakers would rely on correlates present in the non-empathetic samples that had not been deemed significant in production, but this was an accepted consequence of a resynthesis approach, although widening and flattening were applied to shorter utterances as well, to test if perception strategies relied on different correlates to production.

Pitch level was altered in Praat by increasing or decreasing the pitch of the entire sample every two semitones. It was increased and decreased until the level reached the upper and lower limits of male and female conversational speech pitch (50–250Hz for men and 120–480Hz for women (Laver, 1994)). The pitch contour was altered using a manipulation in Praat and removing all but ‘turning points’ in the pitch contour. These were then widened by increasing the distance from the mean (above or below) by one semitone until the upper or lower conversational limit was reached, and flattened by bringing each point towards the mean by one semitone until no longer possible. Certain contour change samples were also subjected to pitch level change, to see if there was an interaction of correlates.

Duration was manipulated using a Praat Script, increasing or decreasing the duration of the accented vowel by 2ms to ensure the change was greater than the Just-Noticeable Difference for segments in natural speech (Huggins, 1972). Duration was increased until it reached +20ms and decreased until the segment length was 0. Duration change was applied to a number of different widened or flattened contours as well to test for interaction.

Creaky voice was initially going to be resynthesised using an open-source version of the Klatt Synthesiser (d’Heureuse, 2021; Klatt, 1980), recreating the formants of the original vowel and increasing flutter as a means of synthesising jitter and shimmer. However, not only was flutter an inappropriate substitute for jitter and shimmer, this resynthesis was not at all natural. Given that creak was only a marker of gender in the production study, it was not important to perfect this, and any effects of creaky voice could be analysed using 4F’s sample (H1-H2=-9.7).

A pilot study following the design of (Yiu et al., 2002) was conducted. All 344 samples were placed into a survey with each block of samples randomised. Ten volunteer participants had to determine if the sample sounded ‘normal’ or ‘abnormal’ to them. Using a binomial distribution table (Runyon et al., 2000) with a 95% confidence level, it was determined that 8 out of 10 participants needed to agree on a sample for it to pass as natural enough for the perception study. Of these samples, 85 of them were deemed normal.

3.1.2 Design

The samples that passed the pilot naturalness test were placed into a survey, with the order totally randomised to avoid task fatigue and shifting criteria. Participants were given a definition of empathy, as well as one of the dialogues from the production experiment that was not the context for any resynthesised sample (Dialogue 4). This was to minimise the possibility of confusing empathy for other emotions, since listeners seem to be at risk of confusing emotions in perception (Breazeal, 2001). The introduction to the survey as described is available in Appendix Three. Participants were asked to confirm their gender, as well as confirming they had not been involved in prior experiments, and also that they were either a native speaker of British English, or were a first language speaker of English who had spent two or more years in England, in order to control for the potential cultural variation across English-speaking areas.

Each sample was ranked according to a five-point Likert scale, since this is cited as a fairly common means of ranking empathy (Yalçın, 2019). Instead of ranking from 1 to 5, this scale went from 0 to 4, with the assumption that a sample could be seen as totally unempathetic, whilst also maintaining the hypothetical notion that empathy could be gradient.

In total, 33 participants completed the survey (20 female and 13 male), all naïve listeners. Participants were given the chance to enter a prize draw with a cash prize after completing the survey. A range of ages can be expected, since they were recruited online, and age was not asked for in this experiment. Given the means of recruitment (through personal connections), it can be assumed that there is a skew towards younger speakers, with a handful of older speakers.

3.1.3 Analysis

Too few samples passed as natural in the pilot experiment to form statistical conclusions about the interactions of correlates in empathetic perception, and so results focus on manipulations of single correlates, these being pitch level, pitch span, and local duration.

The Likert data from the experiment was analysed in SPSS. The first test was a Repeated Measures Ordinal Logistic Regression (RMOL) via a Generalised Estimating Equation function. This test was used as it is appropriate for ordinal data such as results from a Likert scale, as in this experiment. Subject ID and Level of Manipulation (either pitch level, widened or flattened pitch contour, or segment duration) were treated as the subject variables, and the gender of the respondent (the rater of samples) was a within-subject variable. The dependent variable in this test was the empathy rating. The test of model effects was the Type III Wald Chi-Square test, which determines whether the predictors are significant and contribute to the model.

The second statistical test was a Friedman test, which is a non-parametric K-related samples test, where the repeated samples were the different levels of manipulation. This provides a mean rank for each of the factors, allowing for comparison, which shows if there is a statistically significant difference between the means for each category.

3.2 Results

As regards pitch level change, the results for both 5M and 2F show no significance, despite their significance in the production study. The Repeated Measures Ordinal Logistic Regression (RMOL) confirmed that in 5M, there was no significant impact of rater gender ($\chi^2(1, N=33)=0.97, p=0.32$), level of manipulation ($\chi^2(4, N=33)=3.05, p=0.55$), or of level of manipulation and gender combined ($\chi^2(4, N=33)=3.93, p=0.42$), presented in Figure 6. Similarly for 2F, (Figure 7) no significant effect was found for level of manipulation ($\chi^2(2, N=33)=0.64, p=0.968$), and neither for gender and level of manipulation ($\chi^2(2, N=33)=1.434, p=0.488$). The gender of the rater alone was close to approaching significance ($\chi^2(1, N=33)=3.639, p=0.56$), although still insignificant.

Figure 6: Overall Mean, Male Mean, and Female Mean Rankings for 5M's Pitch Samples.

Figure 7: Overall Mean, Male Mean, and Female Mean Rankings for 2F's Pitch Samples.

The Friedman test confirmed that for both 5M ($\chi^2(4, N=33)=3.93, p=0.42$) and 2F ($\chi^2(2, N=32)=0.282, p=0.868$) that no level of manipulation was significant, and thus that listeners did not perceive any level of manipulation to be more empathetic than another at a statistically significant level.

For the widening and flattening of the pitch contour, the image was the same. The RMOL for 2F showed no significant effects for gender ($\chi^2(1, N=50)=0.829, p=0.591$), level of manipulation ($\chi^2(1, N=50)=0.004, p=0.952$), or the two combined ($\chi^2(1, N=50)=0.29, p=0.778$), confirmed by a Friedman test ($\chi^2(1, N=33)=0.474, p=0.491$). 5M also showed no significance in the RMOL for gender ($\chi^2(1, N=16.7)=0.879, p=0.349$), level of manipulation ($\chi^2(5, N=16.7)=6.425, p=0.267$) or the two combined ($\chi^2(5, N=16.7)=2.479, p=0.780$), with insignificance confirmed by a Friedman test ($\chi^2(5, N=33)=7.022, p=0.219$).

The shorter utterances were similarly insignificant for pitch widening or flattening: 4F was not significant for rater gender ($\chi^2(1, N=6.3)=2.494, p=0.114$), level of manipulation ($\chi^2(15, N=6.3)=8.619, p=0.897$), or the two combined ($\chi^2(15, N=6.3)=4.223, p=0.997$), verified with a Friedman test ($\chi^2(15, N=32)=9.526, p=0.848$). Gender ($\chi^2(2, N=33)=2.318, p=0.126$), level of manipulation ($\chi^2(2, N=33)=0.613, p=0.736$) and the two combined ($\chi^2(2, N=33)=0.415, p=0.813$) were not significant for 1M either, also verified by a Friedman test ($\chi^2(2, N=33)=2.333, p=0.311$).

Duration was only incorporated into (and thus investigated in) shorter stimuli, but both speakers' results show different significances. 1M showed no significance at all in the RMOL for level of manipulation ($\chi^2(2, N=33)=1.110, p=0.574$) or gender and level combined ($\chi^2(2, N=33)=0.618, p=0.734$), but showed a very strong significance for the gender of the rater ($\chi^2(1, N=33)=6.897, p=0.009$), as demonstrated in Figure 8. The Friedman test confirmed that no level of manipulation was significantly more empathetic to listeners as a whole ($\chi^2(2, N=33)=3.057, p=0.217$). Individual ANOVAs conducted on each increased duration showed that gender was particularly salient for a duration of +10ms, which was ranked significantly lower by female raters ($F(1, 31)=4.868, p=0.035$). This potentially indicates increased significance of gender when duration changes become more extreme, especially since Figure 8 seems to show this gender division widening with increased duration.

Figure 8: Overall Mean, Male Mean, and Female Mean Rankings for 4F's Duration Samples.

Figure 9: Overall Mean, Male Mean, and Female Mean Rankings for 1M's Duration Samples.

For 4F, however, the level of manipulation was confirmed by the RMOL to be statistically significant ($\chi^2(1, N=25)=9.187, p=0.027$), where gender of the rater ($\chi^2(1, N=25)=2.014, p=0.156$) and gender and level combined ($\chi^2(1, N=25)=4.148, p=0.246$) were not (Figure 9). This significance was re-confirmed by a Friedman test ($\chi^2(3, N=33)=9.128, p=0.028$). It was found that a duration of +4ms was the highest-ranked sample in the Friedman test, which means that for 4F, an increase in duration of 4ms on the accented vowel elicited maximal perceived empathy in this context. This result is drastically different from the 9.3 millisecond decrease between non-empathetic and empathetic conditions produced by 4F in stimulus 3 of the production study. A duration increase of +2ms approached significance in a Friedman test once the

+4ms sample was removed ($\chi^2(2, N=33)=5.763, p=0.056$), which indicates a potential element of gradience, but since this result is not actually significant, this conclusion can only be tentative.

3.3 Discussion

The results of the perception study are noticeably different from the production study. Where pitch level and span were key cues for empathy in longer utterances in the production study, they were insignificant in the perception study. Pitch contour change (which changes span) was, as expected, found to be insignificant for shorter utterances. Duration produced significant effects in shorter utterances, per the production study, but only for 4F did it show significance relating to the level of manipulation. For 1M, on the other hand, it was found that only the gender of the person rating the samples was significant, where females rated samples significantly lower than males, which cannot be definitively attributed to gender-based differences in empathy perception.

These results clearly paint a different picture to the results found for the production study, and this may be for several reasons. Firstly, the removal of the context for those listening may have altered how empathetic the speech was perceived to be, and the correlates that were salient in production were context-dependent. Alternatively, the resyntheses, although passing a naturalness pilot test, may still be in some way unnatural to listeners, which could cause interference with how empathetic they perceived the samples to be. This could potentially explain the significant result in 4F's sample that matches what was found in the production study, as the creaky voice appeared to minimise the naturalness problem by disguising changes in pitch or duration; 37 of the 85 samples that passed the pilot test were from 4F, implying that creaky voice can aid with natural resynthesis. On the other hand, it may simply be that correlates such as a lowering of pitch or reduction of span by flattening the pitch contour are far less salient in perception than they are in production, but given the strength of the significance in production, this seems unlikely.

Participants were not asked to offer feedback on the experiment, but several did. One participant (F;22) said that she found the shorter utterances harder to distinguish than the longer utterances. Another participant (M;22) said he found the decision process to be 'largely arbitrary' based on whether a speaker sounded 'nice or insincere', which indicates that the judgements were not based on conscious criteria, although this does not discount naturalness having a subconscious influence on decisions. Two participants (M;54 and F;30) independent of one another said that their judgements were based on what they thought the speaker was going to say next: the male participant said 'I found myself imagining what the next words coming out of their mouths would be — some of them I thought were more interested to talk about themselves, others would have followed with a 'but...'. The female speaker said that 'sometimes you could hear the unspoken 'but', which again demonstrates that respondents were not basing judgements on conscious decisions of correlates or naturalness, but rather intuitive judgment, which does not rule out the influence of naturalness issues.

Another participant (F;21) said that on the whole, she found that she felt the female voices to be more empathetic across the board, which suggests possible socio-cultural influences. The significant difference in ranking based on the gender of the rater in 1M seems to support some kind of gender-based variation in empathetic perception as noted by the participant F;21. However, it seems limited in scope given that this was the only sample for which there was a difference, and it was only at extreme variations in duration that this occurred to a significant level. It could, therefore, be attributable to female respondents noticing less natural samples and rating them as less empathetic, rather than this being a concrete cue to gender-based differences in empathy.

Given the fact that 4F's samples appear to have been more perceptually natural to participants in the pilot experiment, the results demonstrating that the level of duration manipulation is significant for participants' rankings of empathy are particularly encouraging. Not only does this increase in stressed syllable length support the duration increases found in previous studies of empathetic speech such as Weiste and Peräkylä (2014), the approach to significance in a gradient fashion appears to suggest gradience in the perception of empathy, although clearly more work is needed to solidify this conclusion. The fact that these results correspond to Weiste and Peräkylä's (2014) Finnish study also indicates that there may be some cross-linguistic and cross-cultural consistency in the way empathy is realised in speech, which counters the idea of secondary emotions such as empathy being completely socio-culturally determined.

Although 4F's was the only sample where the results matched those of the production study, it does seem to point towards the idea that, with natural enough samples, the perception of empathetic correlates may match those that are most significant in the production of empathy.

3.3.1 Interim Summary

These results demonstrate the importance of naturalness in empathy perception: although the resynthesised samples passed the pilot naturalness test, the best explanation for the insignificance of these results is a subconscious sensitivity to the naturalness of samples. This could also provide an explanation for the gender divide in the perception of 1M's resynthesised samples, especially since this significance only appeared at the extremes of duration change. This naturalness issue is an accepted shortfall of parametric synthesis, although perhaps a total resynthesis would place respondents into a position where they accept the samples to be entirely artificial and are not subconsciously affected by otherwise perfectly human-sounding voices having elements of unnaturalness.

The results for 4F, where the creak seems to have disguised some of these naturalness issues, are indeed promising. The significance of increasing the accented segment duration in both the production and perception studies for shorter utterances indicates that it is the same correlates that are targeted in perception as in production, regardless of the gender of the person listening. This points towards a model of empathy governed by utterance length rather than gender of speaker or listener, production or perception, or a fixed set of correlates across the board.

4 Discussion

The results from both of these experiments show differences not just between empathy production and perception, although this could be a consequence of the naturalness of samples, but also that within production and perception, there is a divide in the treatment of longer and shorter empathetic productions. This helps to show that empathy is not unified in speech, as previous studies such as McHenry et al. (2012) or Weiste and Peräkylä (2014) convey. However, the fact that the results of this study are in agreement with some of the previous results, which use a different dialect of English and a different language respectively, seems to imply a cross-cultural consistency in at least some aspects of empathetic realisation.

Correlates, such as intensity and precision, that have been used in other emotional speech studies were not included in the analysis of the recorded samples. This could potentially alter the overarching conclusions drawn on the perception of empathy, but a clear image of empathy is created through analysing pitch and duration in particular. Empathetic speech appears to be divided between shorter and longer

utterances, where shorter utterances signal empathy more through local duration increase, and longer ones through a decrease in both pitch level and span.

The results from the perception experiment are hindered by their naturalness, but where this is overcome in 4F's sample, it seems that the results from the perception experiment match those of the production experiment, and there is potentially even some kind of gradience, which provides evidence for Boukricha et al.'s (2013) underlying assumption of gradience in empathy. Of course, all conclusions drawn at this stage must be tentative, due to the insignificance of any other factors in other samples in relation to empathy, and further work must be done with more natural samples, or indeed samples that are further from the natural voice to avoid unwanted subconscious interferences from naturalness. However, the difference between longer and shorter empathetic utterances still holds, as the only results that showed significance were shorter empathetic utterances.

The discrepancy between theoretical predictions and the empirical production evidence can be explained by the fact that acted speech does not behave the same way as natural speech (Johnstone & Scherer, 1999), and as such it would be prudent to explore other contexts in which empathy is elicited alongside this acted speech context, to see if these discrepancies are methodological or part of the nature of empathy itself.

4.1 Limitations

The naturalness of a parametric approach proved to be an obstacle in obtaining results in the perception study. Although resynthesis was chosen over synthesis from scratch to increase the naturalness of samples, and although a pilot naturalness test was conducted, it seemed that naturalness was still an issue for the empathy perception samples. It could be the case that this resynthesis approach created a kind of acoustic 'uncanny valley' effect, where samples were close to sounding completely natural, but there were elements of unnatural speech sufficient to influence empathy rankings in participants. Experiments using resynthesis versus synthesis are necessary to verify this and ensure that the discrepancy between production and perception was methodological.

This study was seriously limited by the COVID-19 pandemic, and it is hoped that further work, free from pandemic-based restrictions, can help solve a large number of the issues encountered. A larger number of participants, recorded in the proper environment, would be possible, allowing for more data to be created and analysed. This could potentially include a larger number of stimuli, as the four stimuli in this experiment constitute a small sample size. In-person perception tests, not possible due to the pandemic, could also allow investigation of intensity as a potential correlate, since in-person tests allow experimenters to control audio output device as well as playback volume. Managing two experiments in a pandemic proved to be particularly difficult with ever-changing restrictions, and it is hoped that future work will not be seriously affected by external circumstances as this work was.

5 Conclusion

There is much that we do not yet know about the behaviour of empathy in speech, and this dissertation has aimed to outline its key correlates, both in production and perception, through a combination of dialogue recordings and analysis-by-(re)synthesis.

Empathetic speech manipulates pitch and duration, depending on the length of the utterance, both in production and perception. This is despite these experiments having different contexts, with the production experiment focusing on acted speech with contexts outlined, and the perception experiment with context totally removed. Lowered pitch level and a flattened pitch contour (narrower span) are significant for longer utterances, and increased local duration of accented syllables (but not increased global duration) are significant for shorter ones. Further research on multi-sentence empathetic utterances could reveal yet another type of empathetic production in speech. Other elements that factor into empathetic production, such as awareness of producing the emotion. This would help illustrate the behaviour of cognitive versus affective empathy, which was not studied in this dissertation. The context of the utterance (e.g., everyday interactions versus clinical settings), has not been explored in detail in this dissertation either, but it is clear that this is another avenue of potential research.

By shedding light on the behaviour of empathy in speech, further questions about the behaviour of secondary emotions in speech as a whole have been raised. More work is needed on how subjective secondary emotions are generally, and how they behave across contexts, as well as how secondary emotions relate to one another. There are indications in this study that there is some cross-cultural consistency. This apparent consistency could be the result of a bias towards studying Western languages, and investigation of non-Western languages and cultures (such as Japanese or Korean) could change this idea of consistency. In terms of speech synthesis, even though the parametric approach is now outdated, this approach works well as a means of testing hypotheses about secondary emotions, but the naturalness of samples needs to be considered carefully for perception studies. Parametric analysis-by-synthesis techniques can also help to explain any potential perceptual issues with secondary emotions in end-to-end text-to-speech (or indeed speech-to-text), as the utterance length sensitivity found in this study may not be picked up on depending on input data. Clearly, therefore, this research is far-reaching in its potential.

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7 Appendices

7.1 Appendix One: Dialogues for Examination of Natural Correlates

Participants alternated between being Speaker A and Speaker B, according to the stimulus; the participant producing Stimuli 1 and 2 is highlighted in yellow, and the participant producing Stimuli 3 and 4 is highlighted in green.

Dialogue 1

(Speaker A is meeting Speaker B for coffee)

A: Hey, sorry I'm late. I sort of got caught up trying to finish my work.

B: No worries — are you feeling OK about your work?

A: Not really — I can't keep on top of it and I have too many deadlines to be able to do anything well enough.

B: It's tricky — I know where you're coming from. Hopefully your deadlines will clear up soon! The coffee's on me this week.

Dialogue 2

(Speaker A and Speaker B are discussing a piece of work)

A: What about trying to solve it with this formula instead?

B: That's hard. I think that's probably more difficult than the way I'm trying to solve it now.

A: Are you sure? I thought it was easier this way.

B: I mean I can try it your way, but I'm not sure it'll work.

Dialogue 3

(Speaker A is explaining a task to Speaker B)

A: It's fairly simple — what you have to do is sort all the emails by the date stamp in the top right corner.

B: I understand.

A: Do you have any questions about it?

B: No, it all makes sense.

Dialogue 4

(Speaker A and Speaker B are talking about a friendship)

A: I've been finding it really difficult to keep her in my life — it's too much of a burden on me.

B: Entirely fair — that's hard. It's tricky when you want someone as your friend but it isn't working.

A: I know, and I feel guilty for it.

B: Honestly, you shouldn't. Sometimes things just play out this way.

Dialogue 5

(Speaker A has called Speaker B on the phone)

A: I think I've taken a wrong turn — I'm on market street heading down towards the church, but I'm not sure how to get to where you are.

B: The church? I know where you're coming from. Turn right at the end of the road and you should see where I am straight away.

A: Thank you! Is it the red door?

B: Yes — just knock when you arrive.

Dialogue 6

(Speaker A is trying to do a video call with Speaker B)

A: Can you hear me? I'm not sure if my connection is working.

B: I hear what you're saying. The issue is your camera doesn't seem to be on. Can you try that?

A: Is this better?

B: That's fantastic — I can see you now.

Dialogue 7

(Speaker A is talking to Speaker B about pulling out of a commitment)

A: I'm really sorry, it's just that I have too much on and I don't think I'd do a good enough job of it at this point.

B: I understand. Is there anything we can do to keep you involved? Like a small side role?

A: I think that could be possible.

Dialogue 8

(Speaker A and Speaker B are discussing difficulties in a relationship)

A: I don't know, it feels like every time I try to bring up a problem, it's like he can't hear me.

B: It's difficult when things play out like that. I hear what you're saying. Is there anything I can do to help?

A: No, it's ok — just hearing me out is enough of a help.

7.2 Appendix Two: Tables of Production Study Results

Table A1: Recordings of Pitch (Hz) to Calculate Level and Span.

Speaker	Gender	Condition	Stimulus	Onset	iH*	L	H*	FL
1M	0	1	4	186.1836	314.6444	185.0633	188.2561	111.1049
2M	0	1	4	171.6812	243.7277	138.5375	170.7096	113.8491
3M	0	1	4	147.4196	223.7096		174.2714	99.3598
4F	1	1	4	243.054	280.0496	178.1281	246.6126	216.3599
5F	1	1	4	254.0662	317.7307	242.7403	304.5188	192.6017
1M	0	2	4	132.8034	177.2732	124.402	132.7516	106.3324
2M	0	2	4	128.6286	146.813	113.9586	133.9459	116.3762
3M	0	2	4	131.8342	159.1047			100.0057
4F	1	2	4	218.7229	213.1621	198.7427	183.1586	179.4615

5F	1	2	4	212.1362	252.3341	177.9944	214.1353	176.0216
1F	1	1	1	217.8663	239.151	196.0871	202.0269	168.3874
2F	1	1	1	209.0436	237.3267	215.7522	236.2947	155.474
3F	1	1	1	215.8901	252.5421	198.1099	215.138	182.8348
4M	0	1	1	182.4433	216.0916	160.7704	163.0261	126.3148
5M	0	1	1	154.7202	169.2912	133.2186	143.5788	113.3869
1F	1	2	1	219.2405	249.1521	198.3934	214.5653	193.2744
2F	1	2	1	210.2398	210.3221	185.1298	196.2252	166.1931
3F	1	2	1	197.1213	205.5711	188.0919	202.9164	175.7269
4M	0	2	1	132.0265	157.8302	133.2666	155.5577	127.1892
5M	0	2	1	128.8578	153.6241	133.3716	139.7998	106.7242

Speaker	Gender	Condition	Stimulus	Onset	H	L*
1M	0	1	3	134.9883	141.5012	101.2258
2M	0	1	3	134.632	142.3951	113.2533
3M	0	1	3	135.2472	141.0034	
4F	1	1	3	227.529	211.8973	
5F	1	1	3	242.4128	269.8936	219.5254
1M	0	2	3	169.9053	177.3776	116.2968
2M	0	2	3	154.2155	160.4436	109.4331
3M	0	2	3	135.5188	137.1657	96.61737
4F	1	2	3	246.2417	242.552	198.1112
5F	1	2	3	226.1611	230.4029	188.0907
1F	1	1	2	245.718	313.6697	263.0393
2F	1	1	2	213.0834	203.8372	179.3743
3F	1	1	2	196.4035	189.6419	164.1068
4M	0	1	2	179.4981	185.7792	119.0717
5M	0	1	2	177.4619	177.9571	112.9983
1F	1	2	2	243.702	228.1987	202.5876
2F	1	2	2			175.8134
3F	1	2	2	203.4197	188.9772	151.5105
4M	0	2	2	144.978	144.5198	
5M	0	2	2	162.8449	151.1602	121.0556

Table A2: *Difference in Global Duration between Non-Empathetic and Empathetic Conditions*

Stimulus	Participant	Deviation from N (%)	Difference (ms)
1	1F	+2.29	+2.2
	2F	+8.88	+9.2
	3F	+10.15	+8.9
	4M	+16.72	+17

	5M	-0.35	-0.3
2	1F	-9.76	-5.7
	2F	+8.05	+4.7
	3F	+2.66	+1.5
	4M	-24.95	-13.7
	5M	+4.88	+2.2
3	1M	+14.07	+8.2
	2M	-13.47	-9.5
	4F	-12.86	-7.6
	3M	+11.61	+7.2
	5F	+20.17	+11.6
4	1M	-14.57	-13.1
	2M	+7.09	+6.6
	4F	+7.85	+7.1
	3M	-33.16	-31
	5F	+1.33	+1.1

Table A3: *Difference in H1-H2 between Non-Empathetic and Empathetic Conditions.*

Long Stimuli			
Speaker	Stim.	Non-Emp. H1-H2 (dB)	Empathetic H1-H2 (dB)
1F	1	-15.5	4.8
2F	1	2.9	-15.4
3F	1	-9.8	8.6
5M	1	-16.3	-7.7
1M	4	-7.8	-11.2
2M	4	-9.7	-14.7
4F	4	-1	-16
5F	4	10.9	11.7

Short Stimuli			
Speaker	Stim.	Non-Emp. H1-H2 (dB)	Empathetic H1-H2 (dB)
1F	2	0.4	3.9
2F	2	7.2	-10.9
3F	2	3.8	10
5M	2	-8.5	-9.2
1M	3	-4.7	-9.7
2M	3	-13.6	-15.9
4F	3	-9.7	-7.7
5F	3	6.5	4.9

7.3 Appendix Three: Survey Designs

Below are listed the introductions to the pilot and main experiments, detailing the instructions that participants were given:

Pilot Experiment

This survey is designed to collect information on perceptions of whether an extract of speech sounds ‘normal’ or ‘abnormal’ (unnatural). By participating in this experiment you consent to the recording of your gender, if you are a native speaker of English, and your responses to whether or not the audio sounds normal/abnormal. No other information will be recorded.

Main Experiment

This test is designed to measure perceptions of empathy in speech. Empathy is when a person can identify with and share the feelings of another person. For example, B is showing empathy in the following dialogue:

(Speaker A and Speaker B are talking about a friendship)

A: I've been finding it really difficult to keep her in my life — it's too much of a burden on me.

B: Entirely fair — that's hard. It's tricky when you want someone as your friend but it isn't working

A: I know, and I feel guilty for it.

B: Honestly, you shouldn't. Sometimes things just play out this way.

In this test, you will hear a number of different samples of voices, some male and some female. Your task is to give the voices a rating from 0 to 4 depending on how empathetic they sound. More simply put, give these voices a rating based on how much you believe they are being empathetic. If a voice does not sound empathetic, then please rate it 0. If it sounds slightly but not totally empathetic, select one of the middle values, and if the voice sounds fully empathetic, then select 4 (the highest value).

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